

A transformations framework for mainstreaming a nature-based solutions approach[☆]

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ABSTRACT

As the integrity and extent of many natural ecosystems continues to decline, the concept of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) is gaining traction as a means to reverse such trends. However, uptake of an NbS approach across society is often piecemeal or partial. This paper argues that a deeper connection with the literature on transformations will help realise the full potential of NbS for enabling sustainable futures. Whilst others have already noted the concept of transformations to be relevant to NbS, many insights from the sustainability transformations literature remain underutilised by those working with NbS.

In this paper, we provide a conceptual framework to enable more ambitious and widespread uptake of NbS. We do this by identifying and drawing on key conceptual perspectives and frameworks from the sustainability transformations literature. This framework identifies key components (current system, future visions, process and an iterative approach) to consider when planning strategic actions. The framework strengthens the links between transformations and NbS concepts for a variety of stakeholders: as well as guiding NbS practitioners, it can also support action-orientated research to help steer NbS to achieve transformational change.

1. Introduction

The integrity and extent of many natural ecosystems continues to decline, driven by multiple human actions [20]. There is an urgent need to reverse this loss for more sustainable collective futures, which will require changes in, and the involvement of, many sectors across society [36]. The notion of Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) has recently gained traction as an important way to re-frame and catalyse more widespread action for change whilst working with nature. NbS is broadly recognised as interventions inspired and powered by nature that address (societal) challenges [76]. We adopt the widely accepted IUCN definition and accompanying global standard that defines NbS as: “actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, which address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits” [37].

As NbS represents an alternative approach to nature, attention has turned to the need for ‘mainstreaming’ [43,72]. We define mainstreaming as a means to normalise ideas considered common in one area of society into other areas to build shared understandings and concerted actions [72]. Achieving this involves institutional change to embed NbS

as the norm for multiple actors and sectors [1] i.e. reorientating how we think and manage nature as relevant to many places and many sectors beyond those interest groups who have traditionally worked for restoration and conservation. In the context of NbS the term mainstreaming remains ambiguous [1]. However mainstreaming is expected to result in changes in collective nature-related practices to make significant contributions to tackling societal challenges [17]. This requires understanding NbS not only as a type of intervention (e.g. wetland creation) but also as a philosophical approach, involving particular ways of thinking (i.e. about the relationship between humans and nature) and acting (i.e. undertaking interventions that seek to harness and strengthen the role of nature for achieving social outcomes, e.g. to reduced flood and/ or drought risk). However, such changes in thinking and acting are both fundamental and difficult, needing strategies that work with multiple levers, including underlying assumptions [19]. Thus, mainstreaming NbS is challenging.

Within the NbS governance literature frameworks for mainstreaming have been developed, for example to conceptualise mainstreaming [1] and emphasising the need to attend to NbS planning, designing and stewarding [16]. However, the scope of the changes needed will entail

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fundamentally changing dynamic patterns of interconnections with reinforcing feedbacks between societies and nature that have developed over long timeframes [18], so entailing transformation at the system level [27]. The potential role of NbS in creating transformative types of change in different socio-ecological systems, by altering the interconnections between individuals, institutions and nature is acknowledged by some, for example Palomo et al. [61] developed a framework to assess the transformative potential of NbS interventions aimed at tackling different environmental challenges. However, achieving this requires a deliberate commitment of multiple actors to work together to plan and implement system-wide transformational change of the wider institutional context to reflect and support the uptake of an NbS approach in the thinking, decision making and actions of multiple actors. Thus, seeking to embed the full potential of NbS entails a system approach that both require and result in positive transformation of institutional arrangements and the type of socio-ecological interventions undertaken within large socio-ecological systems (understood as entailing multiple complex human-nature interconnections and encompassing large numbers of actors, institutions and geographies [85]).

To date, the achievements associated with putting NbS into practice have been piecemeal and slow [55]. These achievements are not, so far, transformative. Therefore, reflection is needed as to whether and how more ambitious (i.e. transformational) change can be achieved. As the sustainability transformations literature fundamentally recognises such change as a complex social process, it offers relevant insights. Conceptual links between ideas of NbS and sustainability transformations have already been acknowledged [89]. There are parallels in the discourse on these topics, as we discuss in the following section. However, much of the literature evaluating or recommending how to improve the uptake of NbS has not yet drawn deeply on the insights of the sustainability transformations literature which is orientated towards fundamental system change (i.e. altering the status quo). Current NbS frameworks either overlook the link between NbS and transformation (see [92]) or focus on the potential of NbS interventions to transform socio-ecological systems (e.g. [61]). Frameworks for guiding the deliberate transformation of institutional arrangements of socio-ecological systems to enable the widespread uptake of an NbS approach have so far been overlooked. The aim of this paper therefore is to assemble a framework explicitly orientated towards guiding transformation to bring about more ambitious NbS, by drawing on the sustainability transformations literature.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. First, we provide some conceptual background about nature-based solutions and transformations (Section 2). Second, we present a transformations framework for mainstreaming NbS, drawing on existing transformations literature (Section 3). Finally, in Section 4 we reiterate our contribution for both NbS mainstreaming research and practice. We believe the framework is relevant to action-orientated research but invite those involved in enabling and leading strategic planning for NbS to share their thoughts.

2. Conceptual background

Here we identify commonalities and complementarities between the literatures on NbS and sustainability transformations. Central to both is a systemic approach that recognises complex patterns of processes and feedbacks involving ecological, technical, political, social and psychological domains [46,51].

2.1. Nature-based solutions (NbS)

The concept of nature-based solutions (NbS) is closely linked to various other concepts, such as blue-green infrastructure and the underlying concept of ecosystem services [3,45]. Conceptual understandings of NbS are varied [22,66] however it is widely agreed that the core idea driving this concept is viewing and working with nature as

a remedy, not a hinderance to human activity, involving interventions that are inspired and powered by nature, address (societal) challenges whilst providing multiple services/benefits including biodiversity gain, are inclusive of a range of actor's needs, and are of high effectiveness and economic efficiency [76]. The IUCN NbS Global standard sets out eight criteria to guide understanding about how well aligned interventions are to the core ideas embedded within the NbS concept [37]. These criteria are intended to inform thinking and action in the design and implementation of nature management initiatives particularly through an online self-assessment tool (<https://nbs-sat.iucn.org/>). The Standard builds on and combines practical experience and academic insights about how to achieve just sustainable interventions in nature management.

An NbS approach therefore frames nature as a way to help address societal challenges and deliver multiple social benefits, in addition to biodiversity improvements [47] with a core focus on developing more sustainable socio-ecological systems [58]. NbS can be applied to help address challenges associated with a rapidly changing climate and other sustainability challenges (e.g. Dubo et al. [97]). An NbS approach therefore differs from traditional approaches to ecosystem restoration that are premised primarily on delivering biodiversity outcomes [88]. Many also consider NbS as a useful pathway to support ecosystem restoration, particularly in rural contexts [40]. The focus on addressing societal challenges also expands the type of actors considered relevant for delivering ecological action beyond the realm of the biodiversity sector to also include actors from other sectors [15]. For example, the NbS concept is increasingly highlighted as useful to help enhance the role of private sector actors in delivering nature-based initiatives to better contribute to ecosystem recovery [12].

Across the NbS literature there has been a strong focus on identifying barriers to the uptake of NbS within different contexts and by different actors (e.g. [58]). Some barriers relate to the ability to delivery interventions (e.g. land ownership) and the evidence base to inform decision-making (e.g. on the ecological outcomes and cost effectiveness compared to more traditional technological solutions) [66]. There is also a strong emphasis on the need to overcome regulatory, political, financial and cognitive barriers [91], including barriers hindering the uptake of and support for NbS by private sector actors [53]. This focus on barriers to NbS within, and across contexts, provides knowledge on current challenges and why change is necessary. Furthermore, the emerging NbS governance literature highlights the need to better understand how to alter existing institutional arrangements to enhance NbS uptake [96], including the need for better strategic planning [6]. NbS governance literature also highlights human agency (the ability of actors to pursue goals and act towards achieving these in ways that align with their underlying values [64]) as important to better enable NbS [51,82]. Where conceptual insights from the transformations literature are starting to inform the NbS governance literature the need to overcome path dependence that may continue to marginalise an NbS approach [2,18] and avoid NbS language being coopted to reinforce the status quo are highlighted [55]. However, solutions-oriented understandings, i.e. how to guide transformations to better enable NbS, has received much less attention to date. Such transformations will need to be driven by collective agency (the ability for the collective action of a group of actors arising from convergence of values, interests, motivations and sense of responsibility [64]) to purposively and fundamentally change institutional arrangements to mainstream NbS as a widely accepted and applied concept [2,82]. Developing and harnessing this collective agency requires multistakeholder processes to co-develop transformational strategies that help fundamentally shift how different types of actors think and act in terms of their relationship with nature.

2.2. Transformations

Transformations is now widely defined from a socio-technical-ecological system perspective as entailing fundamental changes in

structural, functional, relational and cognitive aspects of systems that result in new, qualitatively different patterns of interaction and outcomes [62]. Attention to the concept of transformations has increased in part in response to the recognition that understandings of change need to go beyond minor tweaking [52]. Such incremental interventions are often insufficient to shift current thinking and acting and hinder the emergence of more sustainable collective futures in the context of complex climate change and ecosystem integrity challenges [26]. There are different understandings of transformations, including deliberate transformations driven by human agency [27] and its relevance in responding to different social challenges, including multiple sustainability challenges [84]. Increasingly an overlap is recognised between studies that focus on the transitions concept [44] with the concept of transformations [23], both of which recognise change as a non-linear process with the need to anticipate and proactively seize opportunities and tackle underlying patterns that hinder the emergence of more sustainable pathways [14,19,49]. This includes a focus on the need to shift dominant discourse, underlying power dynamics and norms that shape unsustainable practices [65]. One key conceptual overlap is a focus on large scale, change at a system level where the aim is to fundamentally alter the status quo. This contributes to how we understand transformation as a dynamic, complex social process. This enriches understandings of large-scale, fundamental change processes [34], particularly the importance of working with formal and informal institutions as a necessary step. Transformation can therefore be understood as an umbrella term where the focus is such fundamental system change [62].

Developing institutional environments and enabling conditions (e.g. mechanisms enabling partnerships, to address different abilities and resources of actors, to design in multiple public benefits and to provide financial incentives [82]) helps support wider transformation, for example by leading to widespread uptake of NbS that deliver through time multiple positive outcomes for different social groups and for nature. Within the transformations literature different socio-political factors (e.g. norms, practices, roles and responsibilities) to bring about such fundamental change are highlighted. There is however an emphasis on actors organising and working together to bring this about in practice [62,90,94]. Also brought to the fore is the importance of working with less tangible factors, such as values, norms and beliefs that shape how actors engage with and interpret the world, including how challenges and ideas are perceived [5,32]. Working with such factors is considered essential for transformation [98]. Yet needs will vary, for example there may be the need to surface shared values for collective agency to lay the foundations for transformation, or (more challenging still) to shift dominant values and norms within formal decision-making processes [35]. Also emphasised is the importance of learning and reflection in guiding action [25] and relationships between different types of actors, for example between public, third sector/community-based actors [57, 90] and private sector actors [11]. The transformations literature therefore highlights the need for actors to work adaptively with multiple, interconnected system features as levers to help guide and embed fundamental change.

From this literature underlying principles can be identified that guides how transformations should be understood and approached in practice. One such principle is transformation as a future orientated endeavour. Deliberate transformations entail different actors working together to steer fundamental change to the state of a system (qualitatively different patterns of interactions and outcomes that leads to a fundamentally different situation from before) [62]. The purpose of change is therefore important to understand to provide a focus for mobilising different actors and resources towards a shared objective [4, 27,48,57]. Future orientation starts by building shared visions that focus on key features of the future. This can draw on existing shared objectives, for example the UN Sustainable Development Goals [84], and/or draw on exploratory and other approaches such as scenario planning ([60], e.g. [77]). Furthermore, defining the purpose also makes more

explicit that deliberate transformations are inherently a normative endeavour, where visions and actions may be contested and resisted [34, 49].

Another principle is the need to adopt a systems perspective [8,27, 29,34]. The focus of transformations is often explicitly defined as a (complex, adaptive) system. This systems perspective draws attention to the need to go beyond interventions that solely focus on a specific factor or system feature, instead bringing to the fore the importance of working with and through interconnections between factors and the processes and feedbacks that have emerged [71,90]. However, how a system is framed and thus the focus of action can vary, from a strong emphasis on nature-people interactions [57] or the institutional context which influence human-human and human-nature interactions [30,63]. Whilst the social dimensions of transformations are widely recognised across these different perspectives, the emphasis on different institutional, technological and ecological elements will vary with how a system is defined [48]. A systems perspective is however important for understanding how transformations can be guided and for planning strategic actions to achieve this.

Adopting a process-based perspective is an additional principle that relates to transformations widely conceptualised as a complex, multi-dimensional social process [44,57]. As already highlighted, deliberate transformation is driven by human agency [34,90], through which groups of actors work to alter how features of a system interact and influence each other over time [27]. This brings to the fore transformations as a complex process of collective action, predicated on developing collective understanding that change is necessary, exploring and developing joined up ideas that could help drive the direction of change [26,50], organising existing resources to support change, and embedding ideas within institutional structures and processes to help stabilise new practices in the long term [29]. Through this process a pathway is created for new patterns of interconnections to emerge [26].

Lastly, the importance of adopting an iterative approach is also an underlying principle inherently linked to transformation. Transformations are widely understood as non-linear and inherently uncertain, particularly where a complex, dynamic, adaptive systems perspective is adopted [27,29]. This emphasises that understandings of contexts, challenges and how factors interact to reinforce or alter outcomes can only ever be partial, thus a mismatch between intentions and what emerges in practice is not unlikely [30]. At the same time this can also mean that small actions may also result in widespread impact [48]. As contestation and resistance may emerge from some groups of actors that can hinder if and how transformation unfolds [34,49], evaluation, monitoring, reflection, learning, creativity and problem solving are therefore all fundamental when guiding transformations [27]. Through this reflection, new insights about needs and opportunities may come about [39]. Transformations therefore explicitly require an iterative approach where visions and strategic actions are developed, refined and adapted over time.

Overall, both NbS and transformations concepts have useful and important parallels and offer mutually reinforcing aspects. The transformations literature highlights the need to appraise and work in different ways with current systems as well as explicitly co-create future visions; and also the need to understand adopting and embedding an NbS approach as a social process which will iterate and evolve. Incorporating these insights is fundamental to both research and practice to support further development of NbS.

One example of a transformation is the Dutch Room for the River Programme, created in 2006 following severe flooding in 1995 that highlighted the failure of traditional flood risk approaches, leading to a focus on developing an alternative approach [68]. This has changed how rivers are managed for floods and drought to one more in tune with hydrological processes; involving a wide range of stakeholders. This was possible due not only to changes in engineering practices, but also in wider societal acceptance of flood risks and supporting changes in policies including a new spatial planning Act such that a wholesale

transformation of the institutional context of flood risk management took place [67,83]. This involved new decision frameworks and a new leadership entity to involve a wide range of stakeholders, coordinate across levels of government and with a remit to apply political pressure for this new approach to be widely supported [95]. However this may not as yet be a full NbS approach as biodiversity outcomes remain challenging [7].

3. A transformations framework for NbS

In this section of this perspectives article we present a framework for guiding transformation for the widespread uptake of NbS (Fig. 1) aimed at supporting strategic planning and research. This framework has been informed by an appraisal of existing transformations frameworks (see Table 1 in additional material, especially Löhr et al. [49], IUCN [38], Sharpe et al. [74] Moore et al. [57], O'Brien and Sygna [59]). The initial selection of frameworks and their appraisal was guided by key principles of transformations from the transformations literature (see Section 2.2). For example, there was a focus on frameworks explicitly focused on transformation, that adopt a systems perspective, involve multiple systems features and potential levers of change, and went beyond understanding what is and what needs to change to also support understanding how to achieve this (i.e. to inform what types of actions should be considered). The ability of multiple types of actors to engage with frameworks was also considered. Underpinning this framework therefore is a relational ontology, that views transformational change as emerging from patterns of diverse interconnections between socio-political factors [42], and an interpretivist epistemology that draws attention to social processes [10] for understanding *how* to approach transformational change. We believe that this coherent framework is a useful heuristic for mainstreaming an NbS approach, being useable by practitioners, helping to tame the complexity in planning for transformation that could be overwhelming, and being

applicable across a range of contexts.

This framework has four key components, each highlighting issues that require attention. At the top, on the left and right are circles which respectively represent (1) The current system, understood in turns of three categories, and (2) A vision for a more desirable NbS future system. Connecting these are (3) Process-based dimensions (a, b), and (4) An iterative approach for learning through and refining for transformations. These components respectively highlight (1) what needs to change and what to retain, (2) what is intended to result from change, (3) how to guide change and (4) how to know if transformation is progressing and supports NbS mainstreaming.

In the subsections that follow we explain more about each of these framework components.

3.1. The current untenable system: different categories

A NbS approach involves the potential to reconfigure human-nature interconnections and thus helping transform socio-ecological systems [36,58,61]. An important part of this involves creating institutional conditions to enable the delivery of NbS more widely, by working to change norms (shared expectations), values (underlying guiding principles) practices (i.e. the routine actions of actors) [31,41,78] and the allocation and distribution of resources to reinforce NbS as a credible and normal option across sectors. Thus, the subject of transformations (i.e. how a system is framed) varies but a core part of transformations involves working with socio-political factors that influence how different actors consider the role of nature across settings and levels of governance, and act accordingly to achieve their aims.

System features are categorised in different ways within the transformations literature, many of which highlight the importance of visible (i.e. resources) and less visible factors (i.e. shared values and narratives) in shaping collective change (e.g. see [32]). The transformations framework supports understanding of the current system by

Fig. 1. A transformations framework for mainstreaming nature-based solutions.

Table 1
The IUCN [38] NbS global standard criteria.

IUCN NbS Criteria
Criterion 1: NbS effectively address societal challenges
Criterion 2: Design of NbS is informed by scale
Criterion 3: NbS result in a net gain to biodiversity and ecosystem integrity
Criterion 4: NbS are economically viable
Criterion 5: NbS are based on inclusive, transparent and empowering governance processes
Criterion 6: NbS equitably balance trade-offs between achievement of their primary goal(s) and the continued provision of multiple benefits
Criterion 7: NbS are managed adaptively, based on evidence
Criterion 8: NbS are sustainable and mainstreamed within an appropriate jurisdictional context

distinguishing practical, personal and political categories of factors [31, 59,61] as different types of levers for change. This categorisation was adopted as the categories are few and broad, with each category being able to encompass multiple system features (i.e. 'personal' encompasses shared assumptions, norms and values), types of levers (not just tangible 'practical' factors) and captures complexity, whilst being easily applied across different contexts.

The first category is *practical* which involves technical, technological and behavioural factors, strategic planning and management responses that directly contribute to a desired socio-ecological outcome. For example, if and how nature-based solutions are prioritised and how these are designed and implemented to deliver different socio-ecological benefits. The second category is *political* that relates to the structures, processes and mechanisms that facilitate or constrain decision-making and collective action. This includes formal rules and standards (i.e. legal frameworks, policy objectives and instruments) economic incentives, and social norms and mechanism for participation [61]. For example, a lack of coherence between objectives and instruments for working with nature across policy domains. The third category is the *personal* category and involves individual and shared subjective assumptions, values, norms, beliefs and paradigms which guide how nature is perceived, the nature and role of relationships between actors [13], how problems and potential solutions are viewed, and the nature and role of collective action [64]. For example, from an NbS perspective pluralistic and divergent values colour assumptions about who is a relevant actor and their role in adopting NbS, and the assumptions about the feasibility of working with nature as a solution to different challenges. Fundamental and deeply held worldviews about nature are often at the heart of change, or lack thereof.

Considering categories of a system and their interconnections draws attention to the need to understand and work with multiple types of factors (i.e. not just practical, more tangible factors) in the design and delivery of transformational strategies for achieving widespread uptake of NbS. It can also help reflect on what already exists that may provide 'stepping stones' to help guide transformation [81], e.g. good practice, existing initiatives, networks or shared values [74] and to reflect on gaps that need addressing to strengthen the potential for transformation. Categorising system features in this way is useful for guiding the (co)-development of strategic actions to ensure those involved do not overlook less visible system features. These less-visible factors may be more challenging to work with, but without which transformations may be less likely to come about.

3.2. A vision for the future: NbS widely adopted as an idea and practice

The framework highlights the importance of a clear vision for the future. Often the purpose of change (i.e. the desired future) is conveyed in very general ways as a broad vision, e.g. more sustainable futures [48]. However, a more refined purpose can be useful, i.e. to avoid a 'one size fits all' presumption, and, in practice, this can also galvanise collective exploration to develop and refine a shared, more meaningful purpose. For example, the procedural detail of scenario-planning often produces great benefits to the individuals involved, potentially assisting in learning and even radical reframing that can support transformations

[9]. Such collective exploration can also support better understanding of the shared values necessary to underpin this new future whilst also providing greater opportunity to explore possible points of resistance [74].

Some aspects of a collective purpose may already be widely accepted. In the context of achieving ecological integrity, this is represented by developments within research and practice to refine our understanding of NbS. In particular, important features in the planning and delivery of NbS are specified in the global standard for NbS defined by the IUCN and supporting guidance [75]. This includes 8 criteria (see Table 1) that encompass a range of social, ecological and institutional factors, which cut across practical, political and personal categories. Working with these criteria can help support collective understandings about the key features of a future where there is widespread adoption of NbS (i.e. by multiple social groups, economic sectors and across geographies). A shared vision for a future which involves the widespread adoption of NbS is therefore already starting to emerge that, when incorporated into a framework, can support a more explicit futures orientation for planning strategic actions. Connecting this to the three categories of system features (practical, political and personal) can help refine and deepen understandings of the purpose of transformations and potential knowledge gaps. This can reinforce for strategic actors the need to work with multiple factors (i.e. visible and less visible dimensions of systems) to achieve the desired future. For example, for criteria 2 methods and tools will be required to help match the scale of the social challenges driving action with the spatial scale of intervention, thus working to develop practical system features. However, criteria 5 will require formal processes of engagement and potentially altering how strategic, more powerful actors perceive other stakeholders as relevant. Criteria 8 explicitly identifies mainstreaming as critical, which is an overarching aim requiring the need to work across all three categories. Exploring such connections in terms of a future system can also inform the (co)construction of shared NbS scenarios and narratives to highlight connections between different socio-ecological interventions and socio-economic challenges to create positive outcomes, which can help the idea of NbS resonate better within specific settings [48]. Through such collective future orientated exploration, new groups of actors may coalesce further around shared sets of ideas, goals, knowledge and values to support planning and implementation of strategic actions. The NbS criteria are therefore a useful starting point as they provide a clear direction of travel whilst also bringing to the fore the normative nature of deliberate transformations.

3.3. Transformation process dimensions

Two process-based dimensions are included in the NbS transformations framework. The first focuses on different types of strategic action and the second draws attention to different progression stages involved when creating long lasting transformations. These specific process-based features outlined in the following sub sections were adopted in the framework as they are easy to understand, acknowledge the need to overcome not just bypass ideas and practices that may be hindering progress (i.e. disruption), support different entry points for strategic planning (i.e. to lay the foundations for transformation or to

implement actions for guiding transformation), and support different approaches to fit the system context (e.g. building on what may have unfolded before strategic planning got underway or creating new entities, understandings or processes).

3.3.1. Transformation process dimensions: types of action

Three broad types of strategic action are highlighted as potentially relevant for guiding transformations in the context of NbS within the framework. First is *creating* actions that entail developing new ways of thinking and doing and accelerating their uptake [49]. For example, developing new rules and procedures to better direct financial resources for upscaling NbS practice [49]. Second is *maintaining* actions to retain, reconfigure and expand existing features that could contribute to achieving desired objectives [49]. For example, maintaining and expanding a community of practice to include other actors in designing and delivering NbS in multiple settings, or improving policy implementation. Maintaining actions highlights how examples of good practice may already exist, requiring efforts that strengthen, refine and/or expand these to other parts of the system. Third is *disrupting* actions to undermine existing features (e.g. that reinforce the continued reliance of unsustainable practice) that are hindering progress towards the desired future [28,49]. For example, undermining shared assumptions within economic sectors that undertaking NbS is someone else's responsibility or is a threat to business activities. It is important to note that these actions are intertwined. Therefore, in some cases, creating actions could lead to disrupting existing practices, beliefs and policies to enable the transformation. Understanding and approaching transformation as emerging through developing different interconnected actions that involve creating, maintaining and disrupting types of action and that connect to practical, personal and political system categories is important for guiding more radical system wide change.

3.3.2. Transformation process dimensions: progression stages

Process-based dimensions also include four progression stages of transformations [57]. These progression stages draw attention to how actions aimed at guiding deliberate transformations need to first support actors to organise around the idea of NbS as an alternative, useful way of thinking about the relationship between human activity and nature, as well as actions that help actors work to collectively embed NbS as a new way of thinking and acting across settings and in the long term.

The first stage is the *trigger stage* and entails recognition that the current system is untenable. This informs the next stage, which is *preparing for change*. This stage informs how challenges are understood and how the current system and its components and their interconnectedness are framed. This preparation stage involves organising resources to be used to help understand drivers and potential solutions (to inform a vision for a future, more sustainable system) that in turn informs the subsequent development of more formalised strategies for transformation. The third and fourth stages are intertwined and form core pillars of transformation strategies [79]. The third stage is *navigating change*, that involves working directly with multiple interconnected system features – political, practical and personal categories – to help catalyse uptake of new ways of understanding and doing. The fourth stage is *institutionalising*, involving the development of appropriate institutions that support transformation [63], for example, by incorporating NbS into corporate sustainability strategies and guidance. This stage is necessary for creating the conditions for NbS to become and remain in the long term the default approach, as opposed to the exception. This involves actions aimed at embedding new ideas and practices into system structures, and decision-making and collective action processes.

Together these progression stages help highlight temporal aspects of transformations [48]. Note the shifting balance between different approaches to knowledge production (e.g. problem orientated and solution orientated approaches [56]) that inform understandings of the need for transformations and for steering an alternative future in practice.

Recognising different types of strategic action and stages of progression brings to the fore the variation in how actions engage with (and frame) existing and emerging system features to normatively guide change. Thus, the process-based dimensions of the framework provide an orientation towards the link between what is and is not desirable and action for bringing about transformations.

3.4. An iterative approach: learning and refining for transformations

The framework highlights the iterative nature of transforming for NbS and the importance of explicitly building in evaluations for reflection and learning within transformation strategies, recognising that transformation is a complex social process. The nature of evaluation orientated activities will vary between the different progression stages of transformation (see Section 3.3 above), drawing on different types of knowledge and utilising different methods. In the initial stages of transformation to understand the current system and what needs to change, knowledge syntheses will be important for understanding what needs to change (trends) and what needs to be retained within the current system. The global assessment reports coordinated by the International Platform for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) [69] is a prime example of such a synthesis. Strategic collaborations and networks of actors are also critical to help drive the transformation process. Stakeholder and network mapping methods can help understand what coalitions exist and how these could be developed further [24] and galvanised to help mobilise resources and understand existing governance challenges and opportunities [54]. For example, by developing stronger connections between science and policy communities and early adopters within industry for collective action. Actor-orientated methods will also be useful to understand if and how actors not traditionally involved in planning and delivering nature management initiatives are getting involved in and starting to take leadership in designing NbS programmes to address relevant socio-economic challenges.

For navigating transformation carefully selected indicators can be useful [70], helping to bring together a range of issues, including process, and multiple sources of knowledge to increase the potential for learning [87], for example to evaluate progress towards the overall purpose of the transformation process for the widespread uptake of an NbS approach. Incorporating indicators into a framework is essential for aiding reflection and learning for actors to adapt and refine strategic actions and can help identify unforeseen barriers and opportunities. However, indicators alone will be insufficient [87], instead these need to be embedded within a broader commitment to learning and flexibility throughout the process, that may involve both adjusting assumptions, timeframes and refining of the vision as experience helps inform understandings about what needs to be achieved and how. Furthermore, system mapping tools will also be important to understand persistent and emergent reinforcing feedback loops that may either hinder or support transformation in the long term and also help cultivate systems thinking of those core actors involved in driving the process ([80], e.g. see [73]). Drawing on adaptive governance frameworks could be useful to support such an iterative approach (e.g. [67]). Thus, evaluating progress will involve multiple actors, require multiple methods and will need to be adequately resourced, yet adopting an iterative approach is critical for the development and delivery of transformation strategies to achieve their objective.

4. Discussion and conclusion

The need for transformations to enable the widespread uptake of NbS is increasingly acknowledged, especially to ensure different societal groups are sufficiently engaged. Whilst the conceptual links have been made between the biodiversity crisis, transformation and NbS and conceptual frameworks developed within the biodiversity and NbS communities, a framework explicitly orientated towards guiding *how* to

approach transformation to achieve the widespread uptake of an NbS approach is currently lacking. Several studies have helpfully diagnosed various systemic barriers to NbS (e.g. [21]): the insights from the transformations literature should help to identify how these could be overcome to bring about meaningful, lasting change. The aim of this perspective article was therefore to incorporate detailed insights from the transformations literature into a framework that can support both research and practice for mainstreaming NbS.

To provide a clear basis for designing, planning and implementing mainstreamed NbS, a framework must have several attributes. It must be multi-dimensional i.e. highlight all relevant issues that need consideration yet be coherent and systemic. The framework builds on three types of factors (personal, political and practical) and we believe these three cover the main issues whilst allowing for complexity of interactions. However, other frameworks adopt different categories of factors and it is

always challenging to get the balance between precision and utility. Moreover, the factors focus on how to plan for change but do not (alone) tackle how to make such changes. Additionally, the framework needs to be relevant across settings, scales, levels and sections of society, to broaden and deep the involvement of multiple groups of actors and economic sectors. Related, the framework should be able to support greater deliberation over the aims of NbS, to highlight any areas of conflict and dissent. We designed our framework to have these attributes.

This framework explicitly draws attention to four key components and their interconnections that should be considered in the development of transformational change strategies for mainstreaming NbS. These key components are: 1. A focus on understanding the current system in terms of practical, political and personal categories [59]; 2. A vision for the future that draws on the IUCN NbS criteria [38,74]; 3. Process-based

	Creating actions that entails developing <u>new ways</u> of thinking and doing and accelerating their uptake.	Maintaining actions to <u>build on and reconfigure</u> existing system features that could contribute to achieving objectives for a future system	Disrupting actions to <u>undermine</u> existing system features (e.g. that reinforce the continued reliance of unsustainable practice) that are hindering progress towards intended outcomes.
Practical levers Technical, technological and behavioural elements (e.g skills and resources available/ type of measures undertaken etc)			
Political levers Structures, processes and mechanisms that facilitate or constrain decision making, involvement of different actors and collective action.			
Personal levers Individual and shared subjective assumptions, values, beliefs and paradigms which guide how people perceive how problems and solutions are defined.			

Fig. 2. A matrix to support use of the transformations framework for strategic planning.

dimensions including different strategic actions – creating, maintaining and disrupting – and progression stages of transformations [49,57]; and 4. An iterative approach requiring multiple methods and sources of knowledge. Our visual diagram (Fig. 1) highlights these components and their interrelationships; whilst the accompanying text and citations provide more details about how to expand on and explore these issues. It navigates the complexity of deliberate transformational change across different systems and settings [33,41] to help clarify what to do, who to involve and when and how to reflect and take stock. This framework incorporates aspects of existing frameworks from the sustainability transformations literature. This did not involve a systematic review of all possible frameworks either explicitly or implicitly orientated towards transformation. Choices were made based on the need to work with complexity, for application across contexts and by a range of actor types. Other frameworks may encompass similar features or add further nuance. Notwithstanding this, by drawing attention to these four components of transformations (current system, future vision, process and an iterative approach), we believe this framework is useful and usable.

Application of this framework can support several types of actors working with or for NbS. Groups relevant to NbS range from nature restoration agencies in the public or third sector, to organisations in different economic sectors and those making policies for such sectors; and solutions-orientated researchers. Firstly, the framework can support practitioners of NbS to discuss and co-create their expectations with others and develop strategic actions to enable more widespread uptake of an NbS approach. This includes ensuring strategic actions target all three system categories (practical, political and personal), working to develop new features, amplify good practice and overcome barriers (creating, maintaining and disrupting actions) whilst recognising which stages of transformations have been addressed and which stages need attending to further.

In the EU H2020 MERLIN project, to support the use of this framework in strategic planning for mainstreaming NbS within different economic sectors, a simple matrix has been developed (Fig. 2) to help reflect on the types of lever and actions under consideration. This could be adapted further, for example to aid reflection on how aligned actions being considered are to the purpose of transformation to mainstream NbS, drawing on the IUNC NbS standards.

Furthermore, the framework can guide exploration of the connections between strategic actions and desired future outcomes and the emergence, or not, of alternative processes and feedbacks by adopting an iterative approach within the transformations process. This framework can support practitioners to strategically plan and guide transformation that enable more interventions that adopt an NbS approach in how they are planned and delivered in practice. This action-orientated transformations framework therefore complements the IUCN Global Standard self-assessment tool that helps NbS practitioners diagnoses progress on how well aligned socio-ecological interventions are with an NbS approach in relation to design and the outcomes that arise. Together this learning can then facilitate the targeting of future efforts to strengthen positive reinforcing relationships within socio-ecological systems and reduce the likelihood of the concept of NbS being coopted which can lead to NbS becoming a less meaningful and useful approach over time.

Secondly, the framework can support researchers to analyse the processes and consequences of attempts to initiate and upscale NbS. Doing so will facilitate nuanced evaluations that fully engage with the multiple aspects of design and settings that interact to shape practices; and help action-oriented researchers to produce constructive insights that go beyond diagnosing challenges and barriers. Applying this across cases can also facilitate comparative work to inform future design and evolution of an NbS approach and socio-ecological initiatives framed explicitly around working with nature to support human activities to contribute towards more sustainable futures. We ourselves are currently collaborating with different stakeholders (e.g. private sector actors from economic sectors with key business resources directly linked to

ecosystems) to trial its use but would very much welcome other thoughts on this. For example, how well does this framework support planning for and navigating transformations across different contexts? How to ensure evaluation and learning is a central pillar for developing and guiding transformation for NbS and strengthens the evidence base for encouraging more widespread uptake across settings and for different social groups? Can refinement of the framework help improve its analytic power?

Lastly, the framework may be relevant to those who seek to enable, fund and/ or govern NbS and related strategic initiatives. It highlights the need to understand transformation as a complex social process, and focus on developing collective agency to plan and deliver fundamental, large scale change (i.e. transformation), working with multiple factors and the connections between them and adopting different strategic approaches to guide change [86]. Additionally, the framework's fourth component emphasizing the importance of evaluation for iteration brings to the fore the need for an adaptive approach, which is essential to broaden and deepen the uptake of an NbS across levels of governance [15]. Therefore, any actors seeking to enable or steer adoption of an NbS approach should prioritise resources for monitoring, reflection and updating strategies [93].

Ideally all these actors, and others, will work together in planning, implementing and reflecting on NbS practice and what helps or hinders this across levels of governance, as achieving transformations is predicated on shared understandings and collective action [50]. Once the need for transformation is recognised, as is increasingly so, application of this framework within deliberative multi-actor processes could support different types of actors to come together to co-develop strategic action pathways to broaden and deepen the uptake of NbS approaches from an alternative, marginal idea and practice to become the default way of thinking and doing.

In conclusion, we argue that deepening engagement with the transformations literature offers a route to better understand how to overcome obstacles to achieving and mainstreaming NbS as an idea and as a practice to enhance ecosystem integrity and climate change resilience whilst also delivering multiple social benefits. We offer a framework to facilitate this, by connecting key concepts from transformations and NbS. This framework is action and solutions orientated. It provides a structure to create deliberate, fundamental systemic change for and through the widespread uptake of an NbS approach. It is intended to help generate a shared framing of the current societal challenges, a vision to work towards and responses for guiding transformative change. We hope that applying this framework will help enable NbS practices and refine future understanding of mainstreaming NbS as a complex social process. The framework may seem complicated and onerous compared to a physical intervention in the environment, but without taking this holistic approach and supported by adequate human and financial resources for planning and delivery, we are unlikely to mainstream NbS at sufficient scale and pace to help tackle environmental crisis linked to biodiversity loss and climate change, meet the internationally recognised Sustainable Development Goals (SDG'S) and deliver on the multiple objectives embedded within policies such as the EU Green Deal.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Esther Carmen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Alhassan Ibrahim:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Kirsty Blackstock:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Kerry Waylen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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